

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN DIRECTION

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Abstract: the article describes the methodology of teaching English to students of the social and humanitarian direction and the use of additional resources in teaching foreign languages to students, increasing the interest and attitude of students to a foreign language through auxiliary educational tools, making each lesson interactive, i.e. active - recommendations have been developed regarding conducting students in the methods, giving them additional lessons after the lessons, and wide use of traditional methods from this process.

Key words: foreign languages, methodological manual, special science, etymology, scientific innovation.

Most of the population of today's rapidly developing world can speak two or more languages. Of course, the first of these languages is one's own mother tongue, and many linguists believe that special conditions should be created for mastering not only the studied foreign language, but also the mother tongue. It is worth noting that the new generation growing up as a result of the reforms in the field of learning foreign languages, from the educational institution to the higher education institution, compares the native language and the foreign language at the same time. they learn It is somewhat easier to study by comparing languages that belong to genetically related and non-genetically related language families, and have a high level and experience in international and transnational communication, through the existing research methods in linguistics. It is a scientifically proven fact. Currently, the textbooks, educational programs and manuals that are being created in order to fundamentally apply the field of education in our country to foreign languages are the practical proof of these goals. Therefore, only a student who knows his language and culture well can learn other languages with love. Learning foreign languages requires such special preparations. Here the question arises - What is the need for a second language? Aiming to create a solid foundation for the future prospects of our country, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan developed a number of decisions and decrees aimed at learning foreign languages, which are considered the most urgent to ensure rapid penetration of Uzbekistan into the world community. In particular, if we look at the decision No. 1875 of December 10, 2012, "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages", its essence is to provide foreign education to young people throughout Uzbekistan. connecting languages, ensuring that the young generation can express their thoughts flawlessly in another language. In particular, the following reforms took place from this decision:

- "In all regions of the republic, foreign languages, mainly English, are taught in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons from the first grades of general higher

education, and the alphabet, reading and grammar are taught from the second grade. 'starts with mastering step by step;

- some special subjects, in particular social and international specialties, are taught in foreign languages in higher educational institutions;

- providing students and teachers of general secondary, secondary special, vocational education institutions with textbooks and teaching-methodical complexes on foreign languages, republishing them in compliance with the established deadlines, will be carried out free of charge at the expense of the circulation funds of the Republican target book fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This decision made a radical change in the education system of Uzbekistan. New textbooks were created for the younger generation, and English was taught from educational institutions to higher education. Some subjects are taught in foreign languages in higher education institutions. By learning foreign languages, we will have the opportunity to be aware of the intellectual potential of the world's youth, exchange ideas with them, analyze the process in depth and compare our achievements and shortcomings with theirs. Striving to learn foreign languages, acting according to the saying "A person who knows a language knows" is a legacy of our great ancestors like Farobi who knew many languages and Kashgari who had a wide observation at the level of comparative study of several languages. In addition, Abdulla Avloni's article "Not Two, Four Languages Are Necessary", published in the "Oyna" magazine in 1913, explained in detail the need to learn a language in order to keep up with the world. Our great grandfathers are known and recognized by the whole world because they were able to deliver their scientific innovations and incomparable works to other peoples in their own language. The science, culture and enlightenment of Central Asia are honored. At the heart of all this, as we have emphasized again and again, is knowing the language. It can be explained as follows that the demand for today's youth is to learn foreign languages: to communicate directly with the countries of the world, to express one's independent opinion fluently and clearly in front of the public, to be a special place of Uzbekistan in the world community. Learning international languages is an urgent issue in order to secure the position and serve to strengthen it. Ensuring and strengthening the international special place of Uzbekistan means that it is necessary to be aware of and analyze the news in the cultural, educational, socio-economic sphere of the global world, as well as in the field of medicine and sports, the great past of our country. and rich culture, as well as the great success of modern youth, should be shown to the peoples of the world. In this case, the language certainly acts as a bridge.

But in addition to listing the advantages of language learning that serve only good, it should also be noted that concepts such as state language, national language, and mother tongue should always be in the first place for all of us. needed. As every independent country has its own state language, Uzbek language is a symbol of the independence of Uzbekistan. Learning another language should not lead to the conclusion that the use of one's own language is restricted. Language is a symbol of the state, a mirror of the nation. It is the human duty of every nation to further enrich, polish, expand the scope of its use, in a word, to deliver it to the next generation in an improved form. The perfect study of foreign languages and the use of each in its place to serve the development of the national language is the basis for maintaining the balance of languages in today's society. In the course of classes organized using innovative technologies, students' interest in foreign languages is increased, and their independent creative skills and abilities are improved. According to the etymology of the term

"innovative technology" in the scientific literature, it means "innovation" (in English innovation - introduced innovation, invention, "newness introduced in science and technology"), and "technology" as a linguistic and didactic concept, "less time", represents a set of rational methods of scientific organization of efforts that ensure the achievement of educational goals by spending effort and money [141]. The use of Cinquain, Brainstorming, Case, Zigzag, Cluster, Project, Method, Mind Mapping as specific methods of innovative technology in traditional pedagogy has brought great results. Below we will talk about new pedagogies that are developing.

1) Artificial intelligence in education. The term "artificial intelligence" (AI) is used to describe computer systems [142]. Artificial intelligence education systems are rapidly entering higher education, colleges and universities. Although many people think of artificial intelligence as robot teachers, it also has its benefits. Applications created for students include intelligent learning systems, dialog-based learning systems, inquiry-based learning environments, automatic writing assessments, and conversational agents. Programs for teachers, although less developed, are programs that help teachers improve their knowledge. It is worth noting that it is necessary to take into account the abilities of students and teachers such as critical thinking, creativity, communication and cooperation. It would be great if teachers, researchers, and other interested parties would develop both sides, i.e., artificial intelligence applications and teaching and learning methods.

2) Learning through open data. More than 250 national, local and municipal governments and organizations worldwide are sharing, creating and using data. These organizations seek to see the data used by the public, and many mature services provide resources for exploring open data. Later initiatives led them to innovative education. So, the question arises - what does open data offer as material? What is its importance in learning and teaching? The main factor is authenticity. Shared information is created as a result of real processes taking place within large organizations. Often, the information used in professional work has a real impact on our life and the world around us. The second factor is the importance of information in increasing the potential of students. This can be a very powerful psychological effect. Students can compare the events happening in their cities, villages, and even in their classes with the events happening near and far. Maybe in this process they can identify the problems and attract the attention of the local or the whole society to this problem. In one example, high school students in Italy were rewarded for building projects while learning about public funding. It can be seen that open data has connected readers, data literacy, transparency and evidence-based actions have resulted in social movements for greater motivation.

3) Dealing with the ethics of information use. The growing use of digital technologies in education comes with ever-increasing ethical questions. There are many ethical issues here, such as who owns the data, how to interpret the data, and how to protect the privacy of students and professors. There have also been cases of criticism of people they are not aware of. Maybe it's just a matter of time. In order to avoid such problems, it is necessary to develop a policy related to data ethics in educational institutions, to obtain consent from students for the use of data, to analyze any data from their interactions, to get to know their opinions about the education management system., the creation of an effective teaching system, as well as issues of student and staff support must also be taken into account. There are currently no official training sessions. For this, teachers should create opportunities for students. In today's

digital world, the mutual exchange of information between institutes and universities increases their effectiveness.

In higher education institutions that do not specialize in the language, teaching English through interactive methods has a good effect, through which students' thinking, receiving and giving information from English, new knowledge about the English language, scientific research in their field can be further developed. It allows you to follow the changes and stay abreast of the news, and it broadens the horizons of students. It is interesting and useful for the students of the social and humanitarian direction to work on relevant material, that is, topics in their profession. For this, the student must first know the meaning, pronunciation and usage of new words or terms in the text. Various interactive methods come in handy for this. For example, the "chain" (chain drill) method. Socio-humanitarian direction students listen to the audio of a new word or term and pronounce it and say the word they have learned well with a translation, and the next student repeats his word without translation and one more word they have learned. adds z. In this way, the game continues until the last student's word, because the word order can help the student who is repeating the words by saying this word only in Uzbek or Russian, and if he can't say it, he will be out of the game. This game helps the student to memorize new words more easily and with interest. The second method: the group is divided into 2 or 3 small groups and they stand in a row and reinforce the words through the game "broken telephone". In this, the first student makes a sentence with the participation of new words and phrases and tells it to the ear of the student standing behind him, and he tells the next student, and the game continues in this way. And the game continues until the last student is reached. The main task of the game is to work together with the team and feel the responsibility to fully understand and deliver each student's opinion. In the process of understanding and delivery, they absorb a lot of information. The first group to deliver their opinion without mistakes is declared the winner. Now it is much easier to work with groups that have mastered words. Students listen to the text through audio and follow its written form. When the audio is played the second time, the teacher distributes the new words from the same text in the same state. The student should fill it in at the same time without looking at anything. The result of this practical work is checked with all group students and errors are worked on. Now the text is divided into 2 or 3 parts and distributed to groups. Depending on the capacity of the group, time is set and they are given a task in the form of a game called "Speaker with Translator", in which each of the students works as a translator and a speaker, that is, he translates the speaker's speech not point by point, but tone by tone, and the next sentence is eloquent. does. This is how the unit works. The rest of the groups observe their mistakes and shortcomings and write feedback on their work and tell them in English about what they have understood with the help of speech and translation. The rest of the groups work the same way. The grade is set by the students themselves. In this practical exercise, each student works for the quality output of his group work. These methods serve to quickly and easily learn words and terms in non-philological educational institutions, to express independent thoughts, to explain to peers, to improve the teaching skills of students of the same level, and to actively participate in optional classes. does. The individual comments given by the teacher to the students at the end of the lesson will be motivation for the students. Groups are assigned the task of finding additional information about the given text or processed texts and preparing various presentations. This will help students to find more information related to the topic, to exchange ideas and connect

their thoughts based on the presented presentations, to use grammar correctly, gives the potential to work independently of dictionaries. It can be seen that the student participates in the lesson because he wants to learn and wants to improve his knowledge.

Electronic educational resources, which are considered a relatively new didactic tool, are one of the advanced directions that provide interactivity in the modern education system. Psychological and pedagogical research conducted in this field shows that the use of electronic educational resources in the educational process is the implementation of innovative ideas in the pedagogical activity of teachers, individualization and information of education, individual education for each student. It allows to determine the learning trajectory, introduce the principles of a competent approach to the educational process, and increase the activity of learners.

Electronic educational resources are a set of software, information-technical, educational-methodical systems that provide a specific goal-oriented educational process.

The main changes taking place in modern education - the change of educational paradigms, the person-oriented approach to learning, the introduction of information technologies - make improving the quality of students' knowledge an urgent task.

With the introduction of electronic educational resources into the educational process of higher education institutions, there was a need to develop a learning model using these resources to improve the learning process and increase the quality of student knowledge.

A model is an artificially created sample in the form of schemes, physical structures, marked forms or formulas. It represents and repeats the structure, properties, and interactions between the object's structure, properties, and elements in a much simpler and rougher form [2].

By the model of improving the quality of students' knowledge in the educational process of students of the socio-humanitarian direction on the basis of electronic educational resources, we mean the description and theoretical justification of the educational process, pedagogical conditions, which ensure the improvement of the quality of social education with electronic educational resources. , we also understand the didactic possibilities. Based on the conducted research, we determined the following components of pedagogical modeling: goal setting and planning of the educational process, teaching methods, methods, organizational forms of admission and teaching, criteria for evaluating students' educational activities development. The model proposed by us, in a narrow sense, has a predetermined goal and methods and tools developed to achieve it, as well as instruments that include the parameters of the evaluation of actions and results.

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